
Final report

Bando young researcher

Le innovazioni biotecnologiche a confronto per valorizzare lo studio delle vescicole extracellulari nell'RT2

Introduction

Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) is a clinically and genetically heterogeneous disease. The current knowledge of the disease limits the ability to predict, at the time of diagnosis, how the clinical phenotype will evolve. ALS is a heterogeneous condition presenting several clinical phenotypes and complex genetics, making it difficult for clinicians to stratify patients in clinical trials. Therefore, there is an urgent need for prognostic biomarkers to be utilized by clinicians at the time of ALS diagnosis.

Cell-free DNA (cfDNA) is double-stranded DNA released in biofluids from apoptotic cells. DNA methylation is highly tissue-specific and provides a robust signal to deconvolve the tissue of origin, also from cfDNA.

We hypothesize that each clinical phenotype is related to the initial degeneration of diverse cell types (mainly neurons and muscle cells) and that the cfDNA methylation signature can help identify which specific vulnerable cellular population leads to a distinct clinical manifestation.

Aims of the project:

- 1) Aim 1: analyzing whether cfDNA methylation profiling helps in patient stratification and the results will be integrated into the mathematical model developed in the project 'Develop diagnostic tools for neurodegeneration' for implementing the prognostic determination of ALS patients.

Results:

Aim 1:

We initially performed a test to evaluate the volume required to obtain sufficient cfDNA for analysis. Regardless of the starting volume tested (0.9 ml, 2 ml, 4 ml, 5 ml or 11 ml), we observed that cfDNA extracted from the cerebrospinal fluid of ALS patients were not detectable. Conversely, plasma-derived cfDNA was obtained with a good yield from both 700 μ l and 1.8 ml of starting material. Specifically, cfDNA fragment analysis revealed the expected size profiles of cfDNA (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Profiling of cfDNA extracted from cerebrospinal fluid or plasma. Representative bioanalyzer fragment profiles of cfDNA isolated from the cerebrospinal fluid of ALS patients (A) and plasma (B). Fragment distribution assessed with the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer System.

Next, we extracted extracellular vesicles (EVs) and cfDNA from the same 1.8 ml plasma sample from ALS patients according to the ONCE protocol, which was also used for the 'Develop diagnostic tools for neurodegeneration' project. The two circulating analytes were specifically extracted from plasma samples obtained from healthy donors (HD) (n = 6) and patients with the following ALS phenotypes: flail leg (n = 6), pyramidal (n = 5), bulbar (n = 5) and classical (n = 6). We also analysed five SBMA patients collected from the University of Padua as additional controls (Fig.2).

Fig. 2: Study cohort representation. Representation of study cohort analyzed in the pilot study.

Regarding the EVs, we determined the concentration, mean and median size. In collaboration with the Laboratory of Computational and Functional Oncology, led by Professor Demichelis, we extracted cfDNA from the supernatant obtained during EV isolation using a dedicated kit provided by Qiagen. The yield was quantified using Qubit dsDNA HS assay, and the quality was evaluated using an Agilent 5200 Fragment Analyzer. Although the yield was low, the cfDNA was not contaminated with genomic DNA. Interestingly, we observed variable amounts of cfDNA across different ALS phenotypes (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: cfDNA quantification. quantification of extracted cfDNA from HDs (n=6) and ALS patients, including flail leg (n=6), pyramidal lateral sclerosis (n=5), bulbar phenotype (n=5) and classical phenotype (n=6).

The cfDNA was subjected to bisulfite conversion to differentiate between methylated and unmethylated cytosines in subsequent analysis (ZYMO EZ DNA Methylation-Lightning Kit). The cfDNA was then used as the starting material for library preparation using the IDT xGen Methyl-Seq DNA Library Prep Kit. The libraries were quantified using the Qubit dsDNA HS assay and checked for fragment distribution and quality using the Agilent TapeStation. The libraries were then run on the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 instrument.

Computational analysis of the deconvolution is ongoing, and this information will soon be used to evaluate the potential of cfDNA as an ALS biomarker.

Implement gene therapy technologies

Background

Cystic fibrosis (CF) is the most common severe genetic disease in Europe and still lacks a definitive cure. It affects approximately one newborn in 2,500–3,000, and the average life expectancy remains below 50 years[1]. CF is caused by mutations in the CFTR gene, which encodes a chloride channel essential for cellular homeostasis. CFTR dysregulation leads to multi-organ damage and progressive loss of lung function, which is the main cause of morbidity and mortality in people with CF[2]. CFTR modulators have significantly improved clinical management of CF, but they are ineffective for the 10–15% who do not respond or cannot tolerate them. Moreover, they require continuous administration and do not provide a definitive solution[3].

In contrast, gene editing allows the root-cause correction of CFTR mutations, offering potentially permanent benefit[4]. CRISPR-Cas gene editing tools have already been shown to restore CFTR function in preclinical models. Among these, base editors in particular allow precise correction of mutations without introducing DNA double-strand breaks[5,6]. However, the main obstacle remains the delivery of these molecular tools into the target tissues[7]. Delivery to the lungs is especially challenging due to the presence of thick mucus, heterogeneous epithelium, and the absence of identified specific molecular targets[8]. Overcoming these barriers is essential to make gene editing a realistic therapeutic option for people with CF.

Aims

This project seeks to correct specific disease-causing mutations within the CFTR gene, by developing advanced nanocarriers for the in vivo delivery of CRISPR-Cas tools as RNP complexes.

Specifically, the work will be structured around three main objectives:

- (1) Identification of high-affinity peptides towards airway epithelial cells, using both experimental screening and AI-assisted design;
- (2) Establishment of a robust peptide-engineered cell-derived vesicle platform for delivery of gene-editing tools as RNPs[9-10];
- (3) Validation of the efficacy of the peptide-engineered vesicles in relevant in CF cell models and in vivo, evaluating the entry into airway epithelium via apical delivery.

Methodology

- (1) Identification of peptides with affinity for airway epithelium.

As a starting point, ten peptide candidates with affinity for primary bronchial cells have been selected from literature [11-13]. Other peptide sequences will be identified by computational approach based on AI-assisted protein design[14-16]. This approach will allow prediction and selection of sequences with maximal functional potential for specific targeting of the pulmonary epithelium, integrating recurrent structural patterns and the biophysical properties of protein-cell membrane interactions.

- (2) Engineering cell-derived vesicles with high-affinity peptides for targeted delivery of CRISPR-Cas9 tools to the airway epithelium.

Our design focuses on gene editing (GE) vesicles for the delivery of base editors, specifically ABE8e-SpCas9. GE vesicles are isolated by ultracentrifugation from culture supernatant of producer cells (HEK293T clone), transiently transfected for expression of the key vesicle components: GE vesicles actively incorporate CRISPR base editor, thanks to a dimerization system, and sgRNA, with a tethering system; they are decorated on their surface with the viral envelope protein VSV-G to promote vesiculation and cellular uptake. Vesicle production has been optimized and vesicle characterized for particle size and concentration (Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis), and protein content (ELISA and Western Blotting). We incorporate in GE vesicles a panel of sgRNAs targeting CFTR exons and to assess the delivery we measure editing efficacy in HEK293T and CF-relevant cell lines treated with GE vesicles: DNA is extracted 72 hours later and Sanger sequencing of PCR on the target locus is analyzed by EditR tool. Subsequently, GE vesicles will be employed to correct frequent CF-causing nonsense mutations, such as R553X, in 16HBEge cells engineered to carry these mutations.

To modulate tropism toward the respiratory epithelium, we started engineering GE vesicle platform using the ten targeting peptides selected from literature. We have already tested the tetraspanin proteins CD81, CD9, and CD63 as scaffolds for peptide display on GE vesicle surface, by Western Blotting analysis and evaluation of editing efficacy. We identified CD63 as the tetraspanin most enriched in our system and generated peptide-tetraspanin fusion constructs by exploiting the two extracellular loops[17-19]. To perform a first screening of vesicles engineered with these constructs, we use NanoLuciferase or Cre protein as cargo for better sensitivity compared to Sanger sequencing. NanoLuc-vesicle screening informs on the binding and uptake of vesicles within 4 hours, while Cre-vesicle screening will allow the quantification of functional vesicles by Cre-mediated recombination (Tomato to GFP conversion in the reporter). A first NanoLuc-vesicle screening has already been performed by treating 16HBEge cells with NanoLuc-peptide vesicles and detecting luminescence after 4 hours. For the Cre-vesicle screening, 16HBEge cells containing the reporter mTmG are under development, as well as the production of peptide-Cre vesicles. Their efficacy will be quantified by measuring the Tomato to GFP conversion after 5 days from cell treatment with peptide-Cre vesicles.

(3) Validation of peptide-engineered vesicles in primary cells and in vivo.

Vesicles engineered with the most effective peptides will be produced at larger scale for validation. With support from collaborators, peptide-vesicles will be tested in primary bronchial epithelial cells derived from people with CF and in vivo. For in vivo validation, we will use Cre-Lox reporter mice expressing the fluorescent protein tdTomato. Nanocarriers containing Cre recombinase as protein or mRNA will be administered, and, upon successful delivery, will induce recombination at LoxP sites, with a switch of the reporter fluorescence from tdTomato to EGFP. Editing efficacy will be quantified by evaluating tdTomato and EGFP expression in lung sections and at the single-cell level.

Results

GE vesicles have been designed using membrane-anchoring residues to maximize the encapsulation of both ABE8e-SpCas9 and the required sgRNAs. They have been characterized for particle size (≈ 120 nm as mode diameter), particle concentration and protein cargo. We tested the delivery efficacy of GE vesicles by measuring editing as A-to-G conversion in HEK293T and CFBE41o- cell lines (**Figure 1**). These findings suggest that all components within GE vesicles are necessary for efficient editing.

Figure 1: Validation and characterization of GE vesicles. A) GE vesicles were produced as a complete particles or in the absence of the ABE dimerization system, the sgRNA tethering system or VSV-G envelope. CFBE41o- and HEK293T cells were treated with GE vesicles and DNA was extracted 72 hours later. Sanger sequencing of PCR on the target locus was analyzed by EditR tool. B-E) Vesicle characterization: particle concentration (B), mean and mode diameters (C) and amount of incorporated editor (D) were measured. E) Immunoblotting experiment on transfected cells and derived vesicles showed expression of cellular (CALNEXIN) and vesicular (SYNTENIN, CD9) markers.

The tetraspanin proteins CD81, CD9, and CD63 have been tested as scaffolds for peptide sequences on GE vesicle surface. CD81 and CD63 showed enriched expression in GE vesicles upon overexpression in

producer cells, with CD63 best performing in editing activity in both HEK293T and CFBE410- cells. Further optimization tested VSV-G:tetraspanin plasmid ratios, showing that CD63 maintained higher editing efficacy up to 1:3 ratio (**Figure 2**). These results suggested CD63 as a strong candidate for anchoring and enrich targeting peptides on GE vesicles.

Figure 2: CD63 as candidate tetraspanin for peptide display on GE vesicles. A) Immunoblot of GE vesicles and correspondent donor cell lysates, comparing our control (GE vesicles) with overexpression (OE) of CD9/81/63. Quantification in the graph at bottom right. B) Particle concentration measured by NTA analysis of the GE vesicle productions. C) Editing efficacy in HEK293T and CFBE410- cells. 72 hours post-treatment DNA was extracted and the target locus was amplified by PCR. Editing efficacy was measured with the EditR tool on Sanger sequencing chromatograms. D) Different ratios of VSVG:tetraspanin plasmids were tested in HEK293T cells.

To modulate tropism toward the respiratory epithelium we generated peptide-CD63 fusion constructs by exploiting the two extracellular loops. A total of 60 CD63-peptide vesicle variants were produced, comprising the ten peptide sequences selected from literature in both linear and constrained form (including a linker "L" in Figure 3), inserted into loop 1, loop 2, or both loops of the selected tetraspanin. The resulting vesicles, encapsulating NanoLuc protein, underwent systematic screening to evaluate binding/delivery efficacy in 16HBEge cells, with luminescence as readout (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: Screening of peptide-GE-vesicles. 60 peptide-vesicle variants were produced containing NanoLuc protein as reporter. The ten peptide sequences selected from literature and cloned in CD63 loops are listed in the table. Peptide-vesicles were produced and incubated on 16HBEge cells for 4 hours prior cell lysis and luminescence measurement as readout of vesicle binding and/or uptake. The heat map summarizes the mean luminescence of three independent experiments.

Expected milestones

- (I) By integrating experimental screening with AI-assisted design, we anticipate identifying high-affinity, specific peptides capable of overcoming the major barriers to apical lung delivery;
- (II) Establishment of a new platform of engineered peptide-vesicles with tropism for the airway epithelium.

Future directions

Future directions include establishing nebulization processes for vesicles, suitable for intratracheal administration in people with CF. This project will support the development of RNP-based therapies as potential curative strategies for CF.

References

1. Fondazione per la Ricerca sulla Fibrosi Cistica: <https://www.fibrosicisticaricerca.it/>
2. Clinical and Functional Translation of CFTR: <https://www.cftr2.org/>
3. Allen L, Allen L, Carr SB, Davies G, Downey D, Egan M, Forton JT, Gray R, Haworth C, Horsley A, Smyth AR, Southern KW, Davies JC. Future therapies for cystic fibrosis. *Nat Commun.* 2023 Feb 8;14(1):693. doi: 10.1038/s41467-023-36244-2. PMID: 36755044; PMCID: PMC9907205.
4. Maule G, Arosio D, Cereseto A. Gene Therapy for Cystic Fibrosis: Progress and Challenges of Genome Editing. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2020 May 30;21(11):3903. doi: 10.3390/ijms21113903. PMID: 32486152; PMCID: PMC7313467.
5. Amistadi S, Maule G, Ciciani M, Ensinnck MM, De Keersmaecker L, Ramalho AS, Guidone D, Buccirosi M, Galiotta LJV, Carlon MS, Cereseto A. Functional restoration of a CFTR splicing mutation through RNA delivery of CRISPR adenine base editor. *Mol Ther.* 2023 Jun 7;31(6):1647-1660. doi: 10.1016/j.ymthe.2023.03.004. Epub 2023 Mar 9. PMID: 36895161; PMCID: PMC10277887.
6. Umbach A et al., *Science Translational Medicine*, accepted for publication.
7. Doudna JA. The promise and challenge of therapeutic genome editing. *Nature.* 2020 Feb;578(7794):229-236. doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-1978-5. Epub 2020 Feb 12. PMID: 32051598; PMCID: PMC8992613.
8. Cooney AL, McCray PB Jr, Sinn PL. Cystic Fibrosis Gene Therapy: Looking Back, Looking Forward. *Genes (Basel).* 2018 Nov 7;9(11):538. doi: 10.3390/genes9110538. PMID: 30405068; PMCID: PMC6266271.
9. Leandro K, Rufino-Ramos D, Breyne K, Di Ianni E, Lopes SM, Jorge Nobre R, Kleinstiver BP, Perdigão PRL, Breakefield XO, Pereira de Almeida L. Exploring the potential of cell-derived vesicles for transient delivery of gene editing payloads. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2024 Aug;211:115346. doi: 10.1016/j.addr.2024.115346. Epub 2024 Jun 6. PMID: 38849005; PMCID: PMC11366383.
10. Kim HI, Park J, Zhu Y, Wang X, Han Y, Zhang D. Recent advances in extracellular vesicles for therapeutic cargo delivery. *Exp Mol Med.* 2024 Apr;56(4):836-849. doi: 10.1038/s12276-024-01201-6. Epub 2024 Apr 1. PMID: 38556545; PMCID: PMC11059217.

11. Jost PJ, Harbottle RP, Knight A, Miller AD, Coutelle C, Schneider H. A novel peptide, THALWHT, for the targeting of human airway epithelia. *FEBS Lett.* 2001 Feb 2;489(2-3):263-9. doi: 10.1016/s0014-5793(00)02236-5. PMID: 11165262.
12. Writer MJ, Marshall B, Pilkington-Miksa MA, Barker SE, Jacobsen M, Kritz A, Bell PC, Lester DH, Tabor AB, Hailes HC, Klein N, Hart SL. Targeted gene delivery to human airway epithelial cells with synthetic vectors incorporating novel targeting peptides selected by phage display. *J Drug Target.* 2004 May;12(4):185-93. doi: 10.1080/10611860410001724459. PMID: 15506167.
13. Soto MR, Lewis MM, Leal J, Pan Y, Mohanty RP, Veyssi A, Maier EY, Heiser BJ, Ghosh D. Discovery of peptides for ligand-mediated delivery of mRNA lipid nanoparticles to cystic fibrosis lung epithelia. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids.* 2024 Oct 28;35(4):102375. doi: 10.1016/j.omtn.2024.102375. PMID: 39640013; PMCID: PMC11617931.
14. Shanker VR, Bruun TUJ, Hie BL, Kim PS. Unsupervised evolution of protein and antibody complexes with a structure-informed language model. *Science.* 2024 Jul 5;385(6704):46-53. doi: 10.1126/science.adk8946. Epub 2024 Jul 4. PMID: 38963838; PMCID: PMC11616794.
15. Derry A, Krupkin H, Tartici A, Altman RB. Unsupervised learning reveals landscape of local structural motifs across protein classes. *Bioinformatics.* 2025 Jul 1;41(7):btaf377. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btaf377. PMID: 40569048; PMCID: PMC12258146.
16. Chen LT, Quinn Z, Dumas M, Peng C, Hong L, Lopez-Gonzalez M, Mestre A, Watson R, Vincoff S, Zhao L, Wu J, Stavrand A, Schaeppers-Cheu M, Wang TZ, Srijay D, Monticello C, Vure P, Pulugurta R, Pertsemliadis S, Kholina K, Goel S, DeLisa MP, Chi JA, Truant R, Aguilar HC, Chatterjee P. Target sequence-conditioned design of peptide binders using masked language modeling. *Nat Biotechnol.* 2025 Aug 13. doi: 10.1038/s41587-025-02761-2. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 40804173.
17. Ivanusic D, Madela K, Burghard H, Holland G, Laue M, Bannert N. tANCHOR: a novel mammalian cell surface peptide display system. *Biotechniques.* 2021 Jan;70(1):21-28. doi: 10.2144/btn-2020-0073. Epub 2020 Dec 14. PMID: 33307791.
18. Wiklander OPB, Mamand DR, Mohammad DK, Zheng W, Jawad Wiklander R, Sych T, Zickler AM, Liang X, Sharma H, Lavado A, Bost J, Roudi S, Corso G, Lennaárd AJ, Abedi-Valugerdi M, Mäger I, Alici E, Sezgin E, Nordin JZ, Gupta D, Görgens A, El Andaloussi S. Antibody-displaying extracellular vesicles for targeted cancer therapy. *Nat Biomed Eng.* 2024 Nov;8(11):1453-1468. doi: 10.1038/s41551-024-01214-6. Epub 2024 May 20. PMID: 38769158; PMCID: PMC11584392.
19. Liang X, Niu Z, Galli V, Howe N, Zhao Y, Wiklander OPB, Zheng W, Wiklander RJ, Corso G, Davies C, Hean J, Kyriakopoulou E, Mamand DR, Amin R, Nordin JZ, Gupta D, Andaloussi SE. Extracellular vesicles engineered to bind albumin demonstrate extended circulation time and lymph node accumulation in mouse models. *J Extracell Vesicles.* 2022 Jul;11(7):e12248. doi: 10.1002/jev2.12248. PMID: 35879268; PMCID: PMC9314316.